

Pathogenicity of fungi associated with a decay of kiwifruit

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Abstract. A decay of kiwifruit was noted for the first time in 9–10-year-old Italian vineyards. Trunk and cordons of symptomatic vines showed decayed areas surrounded and preceded by wood discoloration. *Fomitiporia mediterranea* (syn. *F. punctata*) was recovered from decayed tissue, whereas *Phaeoacremonium parasiticum*, *Cadophora malorum* and strains of *Phaeoacremonium aleophilum*, were found in the discolored wood. Two-year-old potted kiwifruit vines of the cultivar Hayward were inoculated with a strain of each species in order to assess their ability to cause wood discoloration and decay. Six months after inoculation, discoloration was clearly evident in all plants inoculated with *Phaeoacremonium* species and *C. malorum*. Decayed areas caused by *F. mediterranea* were observed only in some potted plants either 15 or 18 months after inoculation. Some of the vines inoculated with *P. aleophilum*, *C. malorum* and *F. mediterranea* shrivelled up completely. Inoculated fungi were always recovered from the discolored and decayed tissue. Both types of wood deterioration observed in the field on diseased plants were reproduced in the pathogenicity tests.

1 **Introduction**

2 More than 70% of the kiwifruit world crop is cultivated in Italy and New Zealand.
3 Kiwifruit (*Actinidia deliciosa* var. *deliciosa*) is infected by different fungi associated with
4 wood diseases (Brook 1986; Di Marco *et al.* 2000). Normally, cultural practices (e.g. correct
5 irrigation, proper soil drainage and pruning) protect the vines adequately by preventing the
6 establishment and spread of wood infections (Brook 1986).

7 A new disease was noted for the first time during 1995 and 1996, in some 9–10-year-
8 old vineyards planted with the cultivar Hayward in Emilia Romagna, a north-central region of
9 Italy where kiwifruit is widely cultivated (Calzarano *et al.* 1999). By 2000, incidence of plants
10 with disease symptoms increased throughout the vineyards. Moreover, the same disease was
11 observed in other Italian kiwifruit growing areas, i.e. Piemonte, Lazio and Campania (Di
12 Marco *et al.* 2002) and Greece (Elena and Paplomatas 2002). Furthermore, a kiwifruit wood
13 decline caused by different fungi, including *Phaeoacremonium* spp., was also recorded in
14 France and Italy (Hennion *et al.* 2001; Nipoti *et al.* 2003).

15 Symptoms of the disease appear on the foliage in late summer as small, pale green
16 spots irregularly distributed on the upper side of the leaf. The spots enlarge and coalesce,
17 developing into a series of irregularly shaped chlorotic areas that soon become necrotic and
18 eventually cover most of the leaf surface. When the disease is severe, the affected leaves tend
19 to curl, wilt and drop prematurely. These symptoms occur on the current season's shoots,
20 which develop from canes trained and growing horizontally along the trellis wire. Fruits on
21 diseased vines are stunted and do not reach full maturity. Normally symptoms appear every
22 year on diseased plants causing reduced productivity and longevity of vineyards (Di Marco *et*
23 *al.* 2002; Calzarano *et al.* 1999).

24 Examination of trunk and cordons of symptomatic vines revealed two main types of
25 wood deterioration. One type was a decay distinguished by a bleached appearance and spongy
26 consistency usually affecting a large area of the woody section. The second type was a wood

1 necrosis that occurred as wood discoloration with a brownish zone of hard consistency.
2 Normally, the spongy decay is surrounded by and preceded by the brown discoloration, which
3 often appeared as streaks in longitudinal section.

4 Based on observations in the field, the wood deterioration started from pruning
5 wounds and spread basipetally over the length of the vine. A survey was conducted in order to
6 identify the pathogens associated with the discoloration and decay process, and to correlate
7 symptoms with associated microorganisms (Calzarano *et al.* 1999; Di Marco *et al.* 2000).
8 Isolations from wood with decay yielded the basidiomycete *Fomitiporia mediterranea*
9 formerly classified as *F. punctata* (Fischer, 2002; Fischer and Kassemeyer 2003). Recently,
10 Elena and Paplomatas (2002) demonstrated the ability of *F. punctata* to produce discoloration
11 but not decay, when inoculated in two-year-old kiwifruit potted plants. In trunks and cordons
12 with discolored wood, different mitosporic fungi were initially identified as
13 *Phaeoacremonium inflatipes*, *Phaeoacremonium rubrigenum*, *Phaeoacremonium*
14 *chlamydosporum* and strains of *Phaeoacremonium aleophilum* (Di Marco *et al.* 2000).
15 Further investigations based on sequence analysis of the ITS1-5.8S-ITS2 region of the rDNA
16 and partial sequence of the β -tubulin gene showed that the kiwifruit strains of *P. inflatipes*
17 and *P. rubrigenum* actually were *P. aleophilum* and *P. parasiticum*, respectively (Groenewald
18 *et al.* 2001). Moreover, based on ITS DNA sequence analysis the strains originally identified
19 as *P. chlamydosporum* were recently determined to be *Cadophora malorum* (P.W. Crous,
20 personal communication).

21 The objective of this study was to evaluate the ability of the above-mentioned fungi to
22 produce wood discoloration and decay.

23

24 **Methods**

25 *Fungal isolates*

1 Isolates used in this study were obtained from Emilia Romagna vineyards and
2 deposited in the Centraalbureau voor Schimmelcultures, Utrecht, the Netherlands (CBS) or in
3 the IBIMET Culture Collection, CNR, Section of Bologna, Italy (CSF). *P. aleophilum* (CBS
4 101006), *P. parasiticum* (CBS 101007), *C. malorum* (CBS 101359) and *F. mediterranea*
5 (CSF 1.98) were stored in sealed tubes on potato dextrose agar (Difco PDA, 39 g/L), covered
6 with liquid parafin (Farmitalia - Carlo Erba, Milano, Italy) and maintained at 5°C in the dark.
7 To revive cultures a small piece of mycelium was removed, excess parafin was drained off
8 and the mycelium transferred to Petri dishes containing PDA. The plates were incubated at
9 25°C ($\pm 2^\circ\text{C}$) in the dark.

10 11 *Plant material*

12 One hundred and fifty kiwifruit vines cv. Hayward were obtained from a commercial
13 nursery and grown in 12 L plastic pots containing 60% of a commercial planting mixture of
14 non decomposed sphagnum peat (Floragard GmbH, Oldenburg, Germany) and 40% perlite.
15 Plants were grown outside in an open frame during the entire duration of the experiment.
16 Potted vines were watered depending on climatic conditions in order to have good soil
17 moisture level in pots, and fertilized in the second and third year, by 3 monthly nitrogen
18 applications spreading the granular fertilizer about 10 cm from the base of the trunk.

19 20 *Inoculation*

21 Two experiments were carried out on either two- (Experiment 1) or three-year-old
22 plants (Experiment 2). A hole (5 mm in diam, and 5 mm deep) was made in the trunk at 15 to
23 20 cm above the soil level using a hand-drill. For each fungus, a mycelial agar plug from 1–2-
24 week-old PDA culture was inserted by means of a sterile spatula, whereafter wounds were
25 covered with a lubricant, amojell, snow white (Sigma, Aldrich) and wrapped with Parafilm M
26 (American National Can – Chicago, USA) to prevent drying. Control plants were inoculated

1 with sterile agar plugs. In both experiments 12 single potted vine replicates per treatment were
2 used. Inoculations were done in February (winter) of 1999 and 2001.

3
4 *Evaluation of the inoculation results, re-isolations and analysis of data.*

5 The inoculation was evaluated by assessing: (i) the ability for wound healing as
6 indicated by callus formation over the site of inoculation; (ii) the presence of symptoms on
7 leaves; (iii) the occurrence of apoplectic strokes resulting in complete plant shrivelling up;
8 (iv) the internal longitudinal spread of necrosis (discoloration and decay) in wood and, (v) the
9 re-isolation of the pathogen from the discolored and decayed tissues.

10 Measurements of internal symptoms were made 6 and 18 months (Experiment 1), and
11 5 and 15 months (Experiment 2) after the inoculation, while re-isolation of the inoculated
12 fungus was carried out 6 and 18 months after inoculation. The assessments of foliar
13 symptoms on the plants inoculated with *F. mediterranea* was made 12 months after the
14 inoculation.

15 On each date six plants per treatment were examined. The Parafilm was removed from
16 each plant, and samples were taken by cutting the trunk 7–8 cm above and 7–8 cm below the
17 inoculation site. The samples were flame sterilized, and then split lengthwise by means of
18 pruning shears. For each treatment, 25 wood fragments, about 5 x 5 cm, were cut aseptically
19 with a sterile scalpel from the necrotic wood and placed on plates of PDA amended with
20 streptomycin sulfate (Merck) at 800 mg/L. The plates were maintained at 25±2°C in the dark
21 for at least 15–20 days. The mycelium that grew from the woody fragments was subcultured
22 once to check purity, and wood colonization calculated as the percentage of wood fragments
23 colonized by each inoculated fungus. The colony morphology of the cultures was compared
24 with the morphology of the original isolates.

1 For each assessment, analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed to evaluate
2 differences in the average length of necrosis. Means were compared according to Tukey's
3 Studentized Range (HSD) Test.

4 5 **Results**

6 Externally, all wounds had healed and the site of inoculation was covered with a
7 healthy callus. Internally all inoculated plants showed some discoloration and/or decay
8 depending on the fungus used and the time of inoculation. Tissue discoloration was also
9 evident in the control (Tables 1 and 2).

10 The mitosporic fungi *P. aleophilum*, *P. parasiticum* and *C. malorum* produced
11 discoloration of the wood and pith, and this appeared as brownish to dark brown necrotic
12 areas extending downward and upward from the point of inoculation. Five–six months after
13 inoculation the discoloration was significantly more extensive than in the control (Table 1).

14 In the first experiment, the average length of discoloration assessed in *P. aleophilum*
15 inoculated plants was statistically higher ($P = 0.05$) than in all other treatments. At 18 months
16 from the inoculation all internal necrosis produced by mitosporic fungi ranged from 38.7 mm
17 (*P. parasiticum*) to 42.7 mm and were significantly different ($P = 0.05$) from those occurring
18 in the control plants (18.8 mm). Overall, the pattern of the second experiment was similar to
19 that assessed in the first experiment. The average length of discoloration caused by all
20 mitosporic fungi was significantly different ($P = 0.05$) from that in the controls at 5 and 15
21 months after inoculation. All the fungal species tested confirmed their ability to produce
22 discoloration. *P. aleophilum* gave the longest mean length of necrosis, although no significant
23 differences were noticed ($P = 0.05$) compared to necrosis caused by *P. parasiticum* and *C.*
24 *malorum* necrosis. Most of the inoculated plants clearly showed black streaks originating
25 from necrotic wood, especially in the vines inoculated with *P. aleophilum* (Fig. 1).

1 All fungi used in the pathogenicity test were reisolated from the discolored tissues
2 above and below the site of the inoculation, with different isolation percentages (Table 3). Of
3 the mitosporic fungi tested, *P. aleophilum* was the one most frequently recovered (66.6% of
4 colonized wood fragments).

5 No foliar symptoms such as chlorosis and necrosis developed on either inoculated or
6 non-inoculated vines. Unspecific wilting of the lower leaves of some of the plants inoculated
7 with mitosporic fungi was observed 5–6 months after inoculation. One of the plants
8 inoculated with *C. malorum*, and two plants with *P. aleophilum* completely shrivelled up 6
9 months after inoculation.

10 Vines inoculated with *F. mediterranea* produced decay around the inoculation point,
11 surrounded by a discolored area (Fig. 2). The average length of white decay plus discolored
12 wood in the inoculated vines was not significantly ($P = 0.05$) different from those produced
13 by inoculation with a sterile plug in the control plants, and the basidiomycete was never
14 isolated from the discolored tissues surrounding the decay in the first six months after
15 inoculation (Table 2). Nevertheless a decay was noticed 18 and 15 months after the
16 inoculation on 50% and 60% of inoculated plants in the first and second experiment
17 respectively. *Fomitiporia mediterranea* was reisolated from 32% (first experiment) and 40%
18 of the wood fragments sampled from the decayed areas (Table 3).

19 Foliar symptoms such as unspecific wilting of leaves were noticed 15 months after
20 inoculation on the inoculated plants but not in the control. Furthermore, among the *F.*
21 *mediterranea* inoculated vines, one plant in the first experiment and three plants in the second
22 experiment dried up completely about 15 months after inoculation. Analysis of the wood at
23 the site of inoculation revealed the presence of a decay in the entire transverse section of
24 plants.

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1 **Discussion**

2 Pathogenicity tests carried out on kiwifruit cv. Hayward provided clear evidence of the
3 ability of all fungal species assayed in this study to colonize wood.

4 Inoculations with mitosporic fungi produced discolorations in the wood of potted
5 kiwifruit vines. The most extensive wood deterioration resulted from inoculation with *P.*
6 *aleophilum*. The high temperatures that normally occur in the summer period (maximum daily
7 temperature above 30°C for 45 or 60 days in 1999 and 2001, respectively), may have helped
8 promote disease development, probably also through the occurrence of favourable conditions
9 for the growth of mitosporic fungi inside the woody tissue, particularly *P. aleophilum*, which
10 has the highest optimal growth temperature (30°C) compared to the other mitosporic assayed
11 fungi (Crous *et al.* 1996; Groenewald *et al.* 2001). Moreover, Di Marco *et al.* (2000) reported
12 that *P. aleophilum* was the species most frequently isolated from discolored wood of cordons
13 and trunks, and that it occurred in 100% of the plants with discolored wood. However, results
14 from inoculations did not clearly show a greater ability of a single tested species to cause
15 discoloration in comparison to the others. Moreover, percentages of isolation from discolored
16 wood of inoculated vines, in the second test especially, were similar for all species and not
17 strictly related to the average length of lesions produced by pathogens inside the woody
18 tissue.

19 Our findings clearly indicate that *F. mediterranea* can act as a primary pathogen
20 inducing internal symptoms of spongy white decay if inoculated through wounds on potted
21 vines of kiwifruit cv. Hayward. Despite the long time required by basidiomycetous fungi to
22 produce decay on young plants (Jahn 1967), decay was noticed 15–18 months after
23 inoculation in our experiments.

24 Elena and Paplomatas (2002) were able to re-isolate *F. mediterranea* from discolored
25 wood but only from one inoculated kiwifruit plant. In our trials the basidiomycete could be
26 isolated from decay only, which in turn occurred in 50–60% of inoculated vines. The

1 discolored area appeared to be a reaction zone to infection produced by the plant as occurs in
2 decay caused by *Heterobasidion annosum* (Eversen *et al.* 2000). According to our results,
3 Sparapano *et al.* (2000a) were able to reisolate *F. mediterranea* from the decayed wood
4 obtained 21 months after the wound-inoculation of two-year-old grapevine grafted rootstock.
5 The same authors pointed out the difficulty of re-isolating *F. mediterranea* inoculated on
6 grapevine.

7 Wilt symptoms normally preceded the death of inoculated plants and did not differ
8 according to the fungus inoculated. The appearance of wilting could be explained in terms of
9 a general xylem dysfunction. In fact, the cross section of potted vines was completely affected
10 by discoloration or decay. Conversely, in the field, foliar symptoms can also appear just as
11 polygonal necrotic areas. In this case wood is usually not completely decayed. Most likely,
12 leaf symptoms in the field could be the result of a combination of factors yet to be fully
13 elucidated.

14 *Phaeoacremonium* species and *C. malorum* have been associated with diseases of
15 various woody hosts including spruce, oak, poplar, beech, cypress, grapevine, olive tree,
16 apricot, date palm and aloe (Crous *et al.* 1996; Groenewald *et al.* 2001; Harrington and
17 McNew 2003). In particular, ability to colonize wood has been demonstrated on grapevine for
18 *P. aleophilum*, which proved to be a primary pathogen of esca (Larignon and Dubos 1997;
19 Mugnai *et al.* 1999; Khan *et al.* 2000; Sparapano *et al.* 2000b; Eskalen *et al.* 2001). Recently,
20 *P. parasiticum* has been associated with “hoja de malvon”, a grapevine wood disease widely
21 spread in Argentina, which has some aspects in common with esca (Dupont *et al.* 2002).
22 Moreover *F. mediterranea* is found in many hardwood genera (Fischer 2000), and was
23 associated with esca on mature and old grapevines (Larignon and Dubos 1997; Mugnai *et al.*
24 1999; Graniti *et al.* 2000).

25 *Phaeoacremonium* spp. and *F. mediterranea* proved to be primary pathogens of
26 grapevine and kiwifruit, causing similar diseases in both vine crops. On the basis of the

1 available data, the similarity of the decay of kiwifruit with esca of grapevine is clearly
2 noticeable with regard to the pathogens involved, types of wood deterioration, infection
3 courts, type of disease development in the plant (a vine in both diseases, which is something
4 that may deserve further consideration), and the peculiar, though not specific, foliar symptoms
5 that the two diseases have in common (Di Marco *et al.* 2000; Di Marco *et al.* 2002).

6 An overall view of the evidence suggests that kiwifruit decay, as a chronic disease
7 associated with different pathogens, might not be reduced to a simple scheme of cause and
8 effect. In view of the demonstrated fungal pathogenicity, further studies are needed to clearly
9 assess the path of the infection and, in particular, investigate the pathogenetic processes of the
10 fungi on young plants before foliar symptom appearance.

12 **Acknowledgements**

13 The authors wish to thank Prof. Giuseppe Surico of the Dipartimento di Biotecnologie
14 Agrarie, University of Florence, Italy, and Dr. Jacqueline Edwards of the Institute for
15 Horticultural Development, Knoxfield, Department of Primary Industries, Victoria, Australia,
16 for critically reviewing the manuscript.

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1 **Table 1. Average length (mm) of discolored wood in potted kiwifruit vines cv. Hayward after**
 2 **inoculation with mitosporic fungi**

Treatment	Experiment 1		Experiment 2	
	Months after inoculation			
	6	18	5	15
<i>Phaeoacremonium aleophilum</i>	36.8a ^A	42.7a	33.6a	41.2a
<i>Cadophora malorum</i>	26.8b	39.8a	27.6a	38.6a
<i>Phaeoacremonium parasiticum</i>	26.6b	38.7a	26.6a	39.6a
Sterile plug	16.8c	18.8b	18.6b	17.6b

^AMeans in each column followed by the same letters are not statistically different ($P = 0.05$).

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1 **Table 2. Average length (mm) of necrotic wood in potted kiwifruit vines cv. Hayward after**
 2 **inoculation with *Fomitiporia mediterranea***

Treatment	Experiment 1				Esperiment 2			
	Months after inoculation							
	6		18		5		15	
	DS ^A	DC ^A	DS	DC	DS	DC	DS	DC
<i>Fomitiporia mediterranea</i>	19.0a ^B	0a	21.0a	29.3a	17.8a	0a	18.5a	20.0a
Sterile plug	16.8a	0a	18.8a	0b	18.6a	0a	18.6a	0b

4 ^ADS = discoloration; DC = decay.

5 ^BSee Table 1.

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1 **Table 3. Percentage of fragments yielding inoculated fungus and obtained from necrotic tissue of**
 2 **inoculated vines**

Treatment	Experiment 1			Experiment 2	
	Months after inoculation				
	6	18		15	
	DS ^A	DS	DC ^A	DS	DC
<i>Phaeoacremonium aleophilum</i>	66.6	52.0	0	56.0	0
<i>Cadophora malorum</i>	50	44.0	0	52.0	0
<i>Phaeoacremonium parasiticum</i>	45.8	40.0	0	52.0	0
<i>Fomitiporia mediterranea</i>	0	0	32.0	0	40.0
Sterile control	0	0	0	0	0

^ASee Table 2.

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Fig. 1. Longitudinal sections through kiwifruit canes showing internal discolorations. (A) *Cadophora malorum*. (B) *Phaeoacremonium aleophilum*. (C) *P. parasiticum*. (D) Control inoculation.

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6 **Fig. 2.** Longitudinal sections through kiwifruit canes inoculated with *Fomitiporia*
7 *mediterranea*. (A) Internal discoloration. (B) White rot.

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